

雲南工商學院
YUNNAN TECHNOLOGY AND BUSINESS UNIVERSITY

**PLANNING AND DESIGN OF A HIGH-RISE BUILDING
WITH SEISMIC DETAILING**

By

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A Graduation Paper

Submitted to the Department of Civil Engineering

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In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of Bachelor of Science

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Supervised By

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雲南工商學院
YUNNAN TECHNOLOGY AND BUSINESS UNIVERSITY

毕业论文（设计）

PLANNING AND DESIGN OF A HIGH-RISE BUILDING WITH SEISMIC DETAILLING

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云南工商学院

Yunnan Technology and Business University

2021 年 11 月

Statement of Academic Integrity

I hereby acknowledge that the thesis submitted is a product of my own independent research under the supervision of my supervisor, and that all the data, statistics, pictures and materials are reliable and trustworthy, and that all the previous research and sources are appropriately marked in the thesis, and that the intellectual property of the thesis belongs to the school. I am fully aware of the legal effect of this statement.

Student Signature:

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2022-01-05

云南工商学院

毕业论文（设计）开题报告

学院 建筑工程

专业及班级 2018 级【留学生】土木工程 1 班

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题目名称	PLANNING AND DESIGN OF A HIGH RISE BUILDING WITH SEISMIC DETAILLING				

一、选题的依据和意义，研究的主要问题，拟达到的目的：

One of the five basic demands of human is shelter. In this technological era, people demand for cost effective long lasting homes with aesthetic elevation views. Thus, reinforced concrete structural frame building system came into forefront. For designing these RC structures specialized structural engineers are essential for our society as their main task is providing appropriate shape and strength of structures.

Planning and designing are important aspects for accomplishing of a project. Before planning, it is necessary to survey for determining the suitability of the proposed project. Consideration of earthquake load is very important to design a high rise building structure to avoid earthquake disasters. The single most important characteristics of any structural member is its actual strength, which must be large enough to resist, with some margin to spare, all foreseeable loads that may act on it during the life of the structure without failure or other distress. It is logical, therefore, to proportion members, i.e., to select concrete dimensions and reinforcement, so that member strengths are adequate to resist forces resulting from certain hypothetical overload stages, significantly above loads expected actually to occur in service.

Bangladesh is a suitable place to implement the project because it has an advanced sea port, largest sea beach and many natural exclusive sights like mangrove forest and hill tracks. The seismic framing structure is necessary for resisting against natural disaster during strong earthquake. So, if we make an advanced design to achieve desirable building strength subjected to the earthquake load, we can earn a higher confidence level. Severity of ground shaking at a given location during an earthquake can be minor moderate and strong. Relatively speaking, minor shaking occurs frequently; moderate shaking occasionally and strong shaking rarely. The engineers do not attempt to make earthquake proof buildings that will not get damaged even during the rare but strong

earthquake; such building will too robust & also too expensive. Instead the engineering intention is to make buildings earthquake resistant; Such building resist the effect the ground shaking , although they may get damaged severely but would not collapse during the strong earthquake. Thus safety of people & contents is assured in earthquake resistant's buildings, and thereby a disaster is avoided. This is a major objective of seismic design codes throughout the world.

The conventional approach to earthquake resistant design of buildings depends upon providing the building with strength, stiffness and inelastic deformation capacity which are great enough to great stand a given level to earthquake-generated force. This is generally accomplished through the selection of an appropriate structure configuration and the careful detailing of structural members, such as beams, and columns and the connections between them. Share wall provision is one of the mossy effective design considerations to reduce the seismic effects.

Traditional concrete design for multipurpose uses buildings have been associated with either beam and slab or edge slab floors typically with 32 ft spans. Occasionally, longer-span floors have designed using ribbed or waffle construction. In recent times changes in the requirements of end-users and in developer's specifications have led to more open-plan floor spaces and larger floor-heights in two-way beam supported concrete floor systems. This has increased spans from 32 ft, even to 33ft and more. The change in span length of the slab is directly related with the beam length and it affects the size of beams as well as columns and footings.

To verify the competitiveness of concrete long-span floors based on cost analyses, this study was carried out as a partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science (B. Sc.) in Civil Engineering.

二、研究方法、研究步骤和所需条件:

Research methods: literature research. Find the relevant literature, understand the key points and steps of construction organization design, and have a general understanding of the content of organization design.

Research steps:

1. To determine the purpose and problems of the research, the primary task of literature research is to determine the purpose and problems of the research, and to make clear whether the literature research method is used as an auxiliary method or an independent research method in the research

project.

2. Literature collection, to determine the scope and content of literature collection, in the collection of documents should pay attention to distinguish the authenticity of documents, and record the source of documents, standardize the collection of documents.

3. The collation of the literature, the collected literature is too messy, so it needs to be combed in order to be better used in the research.

4. There are two stages in the process of literature interpretation. in the first stage, we strive to browse the literature in a relatively short period of time, the purpose of which is to locate the literature and facilitate future research and use. The second stage is accuracy, which defines the real value and significance of the literature and makes a correct and objective evaluation.

Required conditions: the use of office, AutoCAD and other software to improve the construction organization design, the preparation of reasonable and feasible construction layout plan and construction progress drawing; Kunming Rongchuangwen Lucheng No. 1 building construction drawings; literature; teacher guidance.

三、研究工作进展计划:

1. 2021年12月05日, 选题, 确定工程项目
2. 2021年12月15日, 指导老师对开题选题进行检查
3. 2021年12月25日, 经评审及修改后, 最终确定并提交开题报告内容和毕业设计选题
4. 2022年01月15日, 提交毕业设计初稿, 指导老师第一次对毕业设计(论文)指导
5. 2022年01月30日, 提交毕业设计二稿, 指导老师第二次对毕业设计(论文)指导
6. 2022年02月10日, 提交毕业设计三稿, 指导老师第三次对毕业设计(论文)指导
7. 2021年04月05日, 最终完成并提交毕业设计(论文)
8. 2021年04月15日, 毕业设计交叉评审
9. 2021年04月25日, 毕业设计答辩

四、主要参考文献、资料:

1. "Bangladesh National Building Code", 1st Edition, City Art Press, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 1993.
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云南工商学院

毕业论文（设计）答辩许可证

经审查，2018 级 土木工程 专业 【留学生】1 班 MD. MOINUL

ISLAM KAWCHER 同学所提交的毕业论文计：**PLANNING AND DESIGN OF A HIGH RISE BUILDING WITH SEISMIC_ DETAILLING**

，符合学院本科生毕业论文（设计）的有关规定，达到了毕业论文（设计）任务书的要求，根据《云南工商学院毕业论文（设计）管理办法》及其它相关文件精神，同意该生提交的毕业论文（设计）参加答辩。

指导教师签字：_____

年 月 日

毕业设计（论文）指导小组负责人签字：

年 月 日

Literature Review

Reinforce concrete is used as construction material in every country. In many countries, including Bangladesh, reinforce concrete is a dominant structural material in engineered construction. The universal nature of reinforced concrete construction stems from the wide availability of reinforcing bars and the constituents of concrete, stones, sand and cement, the relatively simple skills required in concrete construction , and the economy of the reinforced concrete compared to other forms of construction. Concrete is relatively a brittle material whose tensile strength is small compared with its compressive strength. This prevents its economical use in structural member that are subject to tension either entirely or over part of their cross section as in beam or in other flexural members.

The structural system of the building is main load bearing carcass and it need to be proportioned by a structural engineer. When an engineer proportioned it, he must consider the following factors:

- Cost-effectiveness
- Adequate strength
- Maintain serviceability limits

Generally, a concrete structure is made of a set of frames which are consisting of several vertical and horizontal members. That is why, it is known as “Frame Structure”. There are two types of building design concepts included in BNBC:

a) Design considering wind and earthquake loads: The buildings equal to or above 72 ft height should be considered for lateral loads in analysis and design of its structural system.

b) Design considering gravity loads only: The buildings bellow 72 ft height do not need to consider for lateral loads and perform analysis and design for only gravity loads.

Planning and Design of High Rise Building With Seismic Detailing

【MD. MOINUL ISLAM KAWCHER】

[A Thesis/An Independent Study] Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of
the Requirements For the Degree of **[B.Sc.]** in **[Civil Engineering]**
Graduate School Yunnan Technology and Business University

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Academic Year	[Year]

Abstract

This study has been guided in the Department of Civil Engineering at Yunnan Technology And Business University with the objectives to prepare a project and thesis and to study about the architectural plan and structural design of a ten-storied residential building in Dhaka. For this purpose, different types of survey have been conducted in Dhaka and necessary data and information have been gathered to successfully complete the project and thesis work.

In recent era, all of the changes in modern building technology are related to the necessity and comfort of human. The building construction takes the form of complex type of building structure to effectively use the construction materials, reduce construction period, and well facilitated building in every corner of the city. These building are equipped with top to bottom residential apartments for new comer city dwellers. But these types of buildings are difficult to arrange to take total advantage of structural, environmental and mechanical system. These need large open space with large loads from mechanical and electrical instruments. The apartments with more intimate spaces need closer column spacing and have fewer vents and wires required for residents comfort. Thus, the modern design is facing challenges to accommodate all of the desired facilities in one building which requires sufficient knowledge of engineers on space arrangement, planning and formation of structural shape of high rise building. Therefore, the study is conducted to learn on the facts discussed.

A ten-storied residential building was planned and designed as per ACI and BNBC codes and specifications where lateral loads were considered. The observation of this study could found several concluding remarks.

Key words: high rise building; seismic detailing; planning & design;

Acknowledgements

" Appreciation message for your supporters in conducting research"

" The message should be less than one page "

This [independent study/thesis] was granted by [grant source]

This [independent study/thesis] would not have been accomplished without support from [Chairman's name], the examining chairman, and [Committees' name], the committee.

I would also like to thank [Expert Name] (for validating research tool).

I am deeply indebted to [Supporter Name] (for supporting in conducting research).

Author Name

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 General

One of the five basic demands of human is shelter. In this technological era, people demand for cost effective long lasting homes with aesthetic elevation views. Thus, reinforced concrete structural frame building system came into forefront. For designing these RC structures specialized structural engineers are essential for our society as their main task is providing appropriate shape and strength of structures.

Planning and designing are important aspects for accomplishing of a project. Before planning, it is necessary to survey for determining the suitability of the proposed project. Consideration of earthquake load is very important to design a high rise building structure to avoid earthquake disasters. The single most important characteristics of any structural member is its actual strength, which must be large enough to resist, with some margin to spare, all foreseeable loads that may act on it during the life of the structure without failure or other distress. It is logical, therefore, to proportion members, i.e., to select concrete dimensions and reinforcement, so that member strengths are adequate to resist forces resulting from certain hypothetical overload stages, significantly above loads expected actually to occur in service.

1.2 Background of the Study

Bangladesh is a suitable place to implement the project because it has an advanced sea port, largest sea beach and many natural exclusive sights like mangrove forest and hill tracks. The seismic framing structure is necessary for resisting against natural disaster during strong earthquake. So, if we make an advanced design to achieve desirable building strength subjected to the earthquake load, we can earn a higher confidence level. Severity of ground shaking at a given location during an earthquake can be minor moderate and strong. Relatively speaking, minor shaking occurs frequently; moderate shaking occasionally and

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The conventional approach to earthquake resistant design of buildings depends upon providing the building with strength, stiffness and inelastic deformation capacity which are great enough to great stand a given level to earthquake-generated force. This is generally accomplished through the selection of an appropriate structure configuration and the careful detailing of structural members, such as beams, and columns and the connections between them. Share wall provision is one of the mossy effective design considerations to reduce the seismic effects.

Traditional concrete design for multipurpose uses buildings have been associated with either beam and slab or edge slab floors typically with 32 ft spans. Occasionally, longer-span floors have designed using ribbed or waffle construction. In recent times changes in the requirements of end-users and in developer's specifications have led to more open-plan floor spaces and larger floor-heights in two-way beam supported concrete floor systems. This has increased spans from 32 ft, even to 33ft and more. The change in span length of the slab is directly related with the beam length and it affects the size of beams as well as columns and footings.

To verify the competitiveness of concrete long-span floors based on cost analyses, this study was carried out as a partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science (B. Sc.) in Civil Engineering.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Objectives of the study are

- 1) Propose architectural plans and elevation of the building.

- 2) Create structural model and perform structural analysis by ETABS of the proposed building including wind and earthquake loads to absorb inertia forces produced by the building structure.
- 3) Ensure safety against seismic force of the building considering shear walls.
- 4) Design different structural elements of high rise building following BNBC and ACI codes.
- 5) Ensure required ductility against seismic loads considering seismic detailing in different structural members.

1.4 Scopes of the Study

Scopes of the study are following:

- ❖ Architectural plans excluding planning of the building are produced.
- ❖ Basic information of the residential building is collected in the Dhaka city only.
- ❖ USD method which adopted in ACI and BNBC codes were used to analyze and design the building.
- ❖ A ten storied residential building is analyzed and designed to resist wind and earthquake loads.

1.5 Limitation of the Study

1. Foundation design was not cover in this study.
2. All structural members are designed using ultimate strength design (USD) method.
3. Total frame is analyzed by ETABS structural analysis software.
4. Project cost is not estimated for the proposed building.
5. Static nonlinear analysis is performed under gravity, wind and earthquake loads.
6. Dynamic analysis is not considered in this study.

Chapter 2 Project Description

2.1 Project brief

Reinforce concrete is used as construction material in every country. In many countries, including Bangladesh, reinforce concrete is a dominant structural material in engineered construction. The universal nature of reinforced concrete construction stems from the wide availability of reinforcing bars and the constituents of concrete, stones, sand and cement, the relatively simple skills required in concrete construction , and the economy of the reinforced concrete compared to other forms of construction. Concrete is relatively a brittle material whose tensile strength is small compared with its compressive strength. This prevents its economical use in structural member that are subject to tension either entirely or over part of their cross section as in beam or in other flexural members.

The structural system of the building is main load bearing carcass and it need to be proportioned by a structural engineer. When an engineer proportioned it, he must consider the following factors:

- Cost-effectiveness
- Adequate strength
- Maintain serviceability limits

2.2 Reinforced Concrete Frame Structure

Generally, a concrete structure is made of a set of frames which are consisting of several vertical and horizontal members. That is why, it is known as “Frame Structure”. There are two types of building design concepts included in BNBC:

- a) Design considering wind and earthquake loads:** The buildings equal to or above 72 ft height should be considered for lateral loads in analysis and design of its structural system.
- b) Design considering gravity loads only:** The buildings bellow 72 ft height do not need to consider for lateral loads and perform analysis and design for only gravity loads.

2.2.1 Slab

Plain and flat reinforced concrete plate with small comparative thickness to its other measurements rests on beams is called slab.

There are three types of slabs based on their shapes:

- a) **Flat plate:** A flat slab is a typical type of construction in which a reinforced concrete slab without drops is built monolithically with the supporting column and is reinforced in two or more directions without any provision of beam.

Figure 2.1: Reinforced concrete flat plate slab

- b) **Flat slab:** A flat slab is a typical type of construction in which a reinforced concrete slab with or without drops is built monolithically with the supporting column and is reinforced in two or more directions without any provision of beam.

Figure 2.2: Reinforced concrete flat slab system

- c) **Edge (beam) supported slab:** Such kind of slab supported beam in both direction. The slab bends into a dish surface.

Figure 2.3: Reinforced concrete beam supported slab system

One-way slab: In such slab, most of the loads are carried in the short direction to the support, whether support are provided on long sides or both sides. If the ratio of the Length/Width of slab panel > 2.0 , the slab will be one way.

Figure 2.4: One-way slab system

Two-way slab: When the ratio Length/Width of slab panel < 2.0 , it is called two-way slab. Bending will take place in the two directions in a dish-like form. Accordingly, main reinforcement is required in the two directions.

Figure 2.5: Two-way slab

2.2.2 Beam

Beam is a horizontal structural member. Generally, they support the load which come from slab, wall.

All horizontal reinforced concrete members are treated as beams.

There are three types of beams

- i. **Singly reinforced beam:** A singly reinforced beam is that one where tensile reinforcements are placed in tension zone only to resist the total compressive force of concrete.
- ii. **Doubly reinforced beam and:** A doubly reinforced beam is that one where reinforcements are placed in tension and compression zone to resist the total compressive force.
- iii. **T – Beam:** The compression zone of such beam is T-shaped; hence it is called T-beam.

There are different kinds of beams based on support conditions, such as: a) simply support

beam b) Fixed support beam c) Overhanging beam etc.

2.2.3 Columns

All vertical reinforced concrete members on which beams rest and transfer their loads. Columns are the parts of the building which transfer the loads coming over it, along with its weight to the foundation. The column are subjected to vertical and horizontal loads .A column is generally a compression member, supporting beam and slab in a structural system having an effective length.

Types of Columns:

1. Tied
2. Spiral
3. Composite
4. Steel

2.2.4 Foundation

This is the part of the building structure located at the base which bears building load above it and transfers the whole building load to the soil. Foundation of a structure may be deep/shallow. Foundation can be configured with footings of the following types based on their shapes and methods of transferring loads on soil.

a) Individual footings:

- Square
- Rectangular

b) Combined footings:

- Rectangular
- Trapezoidal

c) Strap footing

d) Mat footing

e) Pile footing

f) Wall footing

2.2.5 Staircase

Stairs consist of tread and rise arranged in a series for purpose of giving access to different floors of a building. The stair establishes the way of communication between two successive floor levels of a building. The location of the stair requires good and careful consideration. In a residential building, the staircase may be provided near the main entrance. All staircases should be adequately lighted and properly ventilated.

Figure 2.6a: Staircase with detail description of first flight

Figure 2.6b: Staircase with detail description of second flight

2.2.6 Shear *Wall*

A wall designed to resist lateral forces parallel to the plane of the wall.

2.3 Design Code and Specifications

The design of a reinforced concrete structural member is based on design method and specifications adopted in Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC) and additionally in ACI code to ensure safety, deformation and crack criteria.

2.4 Material

Used building materials are concrete and steel as reinforcement bars. Concrete is basically a mixture of coarse aggregates (stone chips), fine aggregates (sand), bonding material (Portland Cement) and water.

2.5 Loads

Loads that act on structures can be divided into three general categories:

2.5.1 Dead Loads

Such loads are constant in magnitude and magnitude and fixed in location throughout the lifetime of the structure. This is a fixed position gravity service load. This includes the weight of the actual structure itself, as well as anything non-movable that is permanently attached to the structure. Such as Floors, beams, ceiling, roofs, pipes, ventilation ducts, and windows.

2.5.2 Live loads

Such loads are different from dead load because they are varying in magnitude and location. The movable loads are defining as live load, such as furniture, cars and store goods etc.

2.5.3 Lateral Loads: Loads from nature such as wind, earthquake load are known as lateral loads. They may change in magnitude as well as location. Such loads act horizontally toward the structure.

2.5.4 Wind Load

The wind load act horizontal on the building. The design wind load shall include the effects of the sustained wind velocity component and the fluctuating component due to gusts. For slender buildings, the design wind load shall also include additional loading effects due to wind induced vibrations of the building.

Method of Wind Load Calculation:

The minimum design wind load on buildings, structures and components thereof shall be calculated, within the scope and limitations. Taking into account the following effects which shall be determined in accordance with the provisions of this section:

Sustained wind pressure,

$$Q_z = C_c \times C_I \times C_z \times V_b^2$$

Where,

$$Q_z = \text{Sustained wind pressure at height } z, K_N/m^2$$

$$C_I = \text{Structural importance coefficient} =$$

$$47.2 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$C_c = \text{Velocity - to - pressure conversion}$$

$$C_z = \text{Combined height \& exposure coefficient}$$

$$V_b = \text{basic wind speed in } Km / hr$$

Design wind pressure,

$$P_z = C_g \times C_p \times Q_z$$

Where,

$$P_z = \text{Design wind pressure at height } z, K_N/m^2$$

$$C_g = \text{Gust coefficient}$$

$$C_p = \text{Pressure coefficient for structures or}$$

components

$$Q_z = \text{Sustained wind pressure}$$

Important Terms of Wind Load:

Basic Wind Speed V_b : Fastest-mile wind speed in km/h corresponding to the level of 10 meters above the ground of terrain.

Design Wind Pressures, P : Equivalent static pressure due to wind including gusts to be used in the determination of wind loads for buildings. The pressure shall be assumed to act in a direction normal to the surface.

Openings: Apertures or holes in the exterior walls of a building or structure. Doors or other openings in exterior wall.

Structure Importance Coefficient: A factor that accounts for the degree of hazard to human life and damage to the property.

Sustained wind Pressure: The sustained wind pressure q_z on a building surface at any height above ground level is an effective wind pressure.

Exposure Category:

The terrain exposure in which a building or structure is to be sited shall be assessed as being one of the following categories:

- (a) covering at least 20 percent of the area with obstructions of 6 meters or more in
Exposure A: Urban and sub-urban areas, wooded areas, hilly or other terrain height and extending from the site at least 500 meters or 10 times the height of the structure, whichever is greater.
- (b) *Exposure B:* Open terrain with scattered obstructions having heights generally less than 10m extending 800m or more from the site in any full quadrant. This category includes air fields, open park lands, sparsely built-up outskirts of towns, flat open country and grass lands.
- (c) *Exposure C:* Flat and unobstructed open terrain, coastal areas and riversides facing large bodies of water, over 1.5km or more in width. Exposure C extends inland from the shoreline 400m or 10 times the height of structures,

2.5.5 Earthquake load

Equivalent static force method:

Design base shear, $V = \frac{ZIC}{R}W$

where Z = Seismic zone coefficient

I = Structure importance coefficient

R = Response modification coefficient for structural systems

W = Total seismic dead load

C = Numeric coefficient given by the relation $= (1.25 S) / T^{2/3}$

where S = Site coefficient for soil characteristics

T = Fundamental period of vibration in seconds $= C_t (h_n)^{3/4}$

in which $C_t = 0.083$ for steel moment resisting frames
 $= 0.073$ for reinforced concrete moment resisting frames and
 Eccentric braced steel frames.
 $= 0.049$ for all other structural systems.

$h_n =$ Height in meters above the base to level n

Seismic dead load, W , is the total dead load of a building or a structure, including permanent partitions and applicable portions of other loads listed below

Vertical distribution of lateral force:

In the absence of a more rigorous procedure, the total lateral force, which is the base shear V , shall be distributed along the height of the structure in accordance with the following equation:

$$V = F_t + \sum F_i$$

where,

$F_i =$ Lateral force applied at storey level i

$F_t =$ Concentrated lateral force considered at the top

of the

building in addition to the force F_n

$$= 0.070 TV \leq 0.25V \quad \text{when } T > 0.70$$

second

2.6 Important terms related to earthquake design concept

Base Shear: Total design lateral force or shear at the base of a structure .

Essential Facilities: Buildings and structures which are necessary to remain functional during an emergency or a post disaster period.

Building Frame System: An essentially complete space frame which provides support for gravity loads.

Moment Resisting Frame: A frame in which members and joints are capable of

resisting forces primarily by flexure.

Intermediate Moment Resistance Frame (IMRF): A concrete or steel frame.

Special Moment Resisting Frame (SMRF): A moment resisting frame specially detailed to provide ductile behavior complying with the seismic requirements for concrete frame.

Chapter 3 Architectural Planing & Description of the Building

3. 1 Introduction

This chapter provides detailed description of the whole structure. The main features can be summarized as below:

Height of building = 118'

Length of building = 79.25'

Width of building = 60.42'

Total floors = 10 storied

Types of floors : Residential apartments.

Safety of the Stricture = Designed as per BNBC and ACI codes and specifications. Capable for resisting 210Kmph wind speed and high Richter scale earthquake affects. 4ksi concrete $w_c= 150pcf$ and 60-grade deformed bars are used.

Figure 3.1: Proposed building location Map

Figure 3.2: Front elevation of the proposed building

Figure 3.3: South elevation of the proposed building

Figure 3.4: East elevation of the proposed building

Figure 3.5: West elevation of the proposed building

3.2 Elements of Different Floors

Figure 3.3: Typical story plan of the proposed building.

Elements available in ground Floor

- Car parking purpose use
- Floor height 10'-0"
- Total floor area is 3776.5 ft²
- Stair cases are used for residences' entry purpose and also will be used for emergency exit purpose.
- Inter floor communication is maintained using Stair case-1, Stair case-2, & passenger lift-1
- Car ways.

Chapter 4 Wind & Earthquake Load Calculation

4.1 Load Calculation

4.1.1 Applied load combination

Applied load combinations used for analysis and design for structural members of the proposed building are taken from the ACI code. They are as follows:

- 1.2 DL+ 1.6 LL
- 1.2 DL + LL
- 1.2 DL+ 0.8WL (L-R) long side
- 1.2 DL+0.8WL(R-L) long side
- 1.2 DL+0.8WL (L-R) short side
- 1.2 DL+0.8WL (R-L) Short side
- 1.2 DL+ 1.3WL (L-R) long + LL
- 1.2 DL+ 1.3WL(R-L) long + LL
- 1.20DL+ 1.3WL (L-R) short+1.00LL
- 1.20DL+ 1.3WL (R-L) long+1.00LL
- 1.20DL+ EQ (L-R) long +1.00LL
- 1.20DL+ EQ (R-L) long +1.00LL
- 1.20DL+ 1×EQ (L-R) short +1.00LL
- 1.20DL+ 1×EQ(R-L) short +1.00LL
- 0.90DL+1.30WL (L-R) long

4.2 Earthquake Load Calculation Based on BNBC Code

Design data:

Height of building, $H = 118' = 35.98m$

Seismic zone coefficient (Dhaka zone), $Z = 0.15$

For special moment resisting frame, $R = 12$

Important Coefficient for residential building, $I = 1$

Total dead loads calculated by ETABS = 21563.2 kip = 9591.89kN

Vibration time period, $T = 0.073H^{3/4} = 0.073 \times 35.98^{3/4} = 1.07$ sec

Seismic coefficient, $C = \frac{1.25S}{T^{2/3}} = \frac{1.25 \times 1.5}{1.07^{2/3}} = 1.8$

Base shear, $V = \frac{ZIC}{R} \times W = \frac{0.15 \times 1 \times 1.8}{12} \times 95917.89 = 2005215815 \text{ kN}$

According to the BNBC code, when the vibration time is greater than 0.07 second then the F_t force is applicable. F_t is only used at top of the building.

$$F_t = 0.07 \times T \times V \leq 0.25 \times V$$

$$\Rightarrow F_t = 0.07 \times 1.07 \times 215815 = 161.64 \text{ kN and } 0.25V = 0.25 \times 215815 = 539.54 \text{ kN}$$

$$\Rightarrow F_t = 161.64 \text{ kN} < 539.54 \text{ kN}$$

So, $F_t = 161.64 \text{ KN}$

$$F_x = \frac{(v - F_t)Wh}{\sum Wh} h_x = \frac{215815 - 161.64}{203.74} \times h_x = 9.79 \times h_x$$

Table4.1: Earthquake load at the floor level

Storey	Height h_x (m)	F_x (kN)
10th	33.55	490.095
9th	30.45	298.595
8th	27.45	268.736
7th	24.40	238.876
6th	21.35	209.017
5th	18.30	179.157
4th	15.25	149.298
3rd	12.2	119.438
2nd	9.15	89.579
1st	6.1	59.719
GF	3.05	29.850
Base	2.44	23.89

4.3 Wind Load Calculation

Width of building, B = 79.25 ft

Length of building, L = 60.42 ft

Height of building, H = 112 ft

Wind pressure in Dhaka city, V_b = 210 km/h

Exposure

= A

Importance coefficient for hotel building, C_i = 1

Velocity to pressure conversion coefficient, C_c = 0.0000472

$H/B = 1.41$ and $L/B = 0.76$

Figure 4.1: Wind load application on the building across short direction

So, from Table 6.2.15 of BNBC we can find windward coefficient C_p .

Story range = Ground floor to Top.

Sustained wind pressure, $q_z = 0.0000472 \times 1 \times C_z \times 210^2 = 2.08152 C_z$

Wind from Short side

From Chart According to the BNBC code corresponding H/B and L/B,

Pressure coefficient, $C_p = 1.48$

Guest coefficient, $C_G = 1.299$

Wind pressure $P_z = C_G \times C_p \times q_z$

$$= 1.299 \times 1.48 \times 2.08 C_z = 3.99 C_z$$

Table 4.2: Estimation of design wind pressure

Storey	Height m	C_z	q_z	P_z kN/m ²	Aera m ²	F kN
10th	33.54	0.892	1.857	3.559	17.5	62.18
9th	30.49	0.855	1.779	3.411	39.94	136.24
8th	27.44	0.816	1.699	3.252	39.94	129.88
7th	24.39	0.774	1.611	3.088	39.94	123.33
6th	21.34	0.729	1.517	2.909	39.94	116.19
5th	18.34	0.682	1.419	2.721	39.94	108.66
4th	15.24	0.628	1.306	2.506	39.94	100.09
3rd	12.19	0.569	1.184	2.27	39.94	90.66
2nd	9.15	0.500	1.04	1.995	39.94	79.68
1st	6.09	0.418	0.869	1.668	39.94	66.61
G.F	3.05	0.368	0.765	1.468	39.94	58.63
GL To GF	0.61	0.368	.765	1.468	39.94	58.63

Chapter 5 Study Methodology & Analysis of the Building

5.1 Introduction

Extended 3D analysis of Building System (ETABS) is nonlinear 3D structural analysis software specially designed for building frame system. Dating back more than 30 years to the original development of ETABS, structural analysis for buildings is easy and simple for both lateral and gravity loads. In this chapter, a brief description about planning, modeling, analysis and design of the fifteen storied residential building is provided.

5.2 Study Procedure

Step-1: Selection and planning of the structure

Fifteen storied frame structure with edge supported floor system and having same plinth areas with different floor plans had been selected to study. The whole structure is a residential building having all the essential facilities in the building.

Step-2: Selection of the material properties & loadings

Material properties (compressive strength of concrete, yield stress of steel, unit weight of concrete, brick etc.) and loadings (service dead and live loads) were selected. Wind and earthquake loads were also considered as horizontal loading in the building analysis.

Step-3: Building Structural Modeling

To analyze a building frame in ETABS modeling of the building frame is mandatory. To create the model grid data and storey data were setup from the building plan grid system and storey data definition tab. A 3D solid element model for analyzing the fifteen storied reinforced concrete building is developed using ETABS structural analysis software. The 3D ETABS analysis model of fifteen storied reinforced concrete building is shown in Figure 3.2. The ultimate strength for concrete and yielding stress and ultimate strength for steel are considered 4 ksi, and 60 ksi respectively.

Figure 5.1: 3D view of structural frame model of the proposed building

Live and dead loads are applied as gravity load and wind load and earthquake load are considered as lateral load in the analysis. Loads of partition walls, floor finish and self-weight of the structures are treated as dead load and live load is taken from BNBC. In the modeling, dead and live loads are assigned as vertical distributed load on all floor surfaces. Earthquake loads are calculated following equivalent static load method for each story levels and assigned horizontally together with wind load at each beam-column joint of exterior surface of the building as user defined loads.

Step-4: Analysis and design of the structure:

The structure is analyzed by using ETABS and corresponding design calculations are provided in the successive Chapters.

5.3 Design data and specifications considered in this study

The whole study was carried out based on few considerations and specifications which are followings:

1. Design code: Bangladesh National Building Code (*BNBC*), 1993.
American Concrete Institute (*ACI*) Building design code, 2008.
2. Loadings: Floor plus ceiling finish = 30 psf
Live load = 40 psf for all floors.
Earthquake and wind load are considered.
3. Building components: Column type = Tied column
Slab thickness = 5 in
Thickness of all partition walls = 5 in
Beam type = Doubly reinforced beam
4. Material properties: Yield strength of reinforcing bars, $f_y = 60,000$ psi.
Concrete compressive strength, $f_c' = 4,000$ psi.
Normal density concrete having $w_c = 150$ pcf
Unit weight of brick, $w_b = 120$ pcf
Maximum Steel ratio for column, $\rho_g = 6\%$ of A_g
5. Sectional properties of column: C1= 16×16 in
C2= 18×18 in
C3=20× 20 in
6. Sectional properties of Beam: B1= 12×18 in
FB1= 15×21 in

5.4 Results of 3D Model Analysis

3D finite elements models are developed based on actual shape of the buildings using ETABS structural analysis software. Besides the gravity loads, wind and earthquake loads, materials property definitions, boundary conditions and elements geometrical property definitions are also generated in the analysis models and run the analysis programs of the models for statics analysis in ETABS analysis platform. Results produced by the analysis are illustrated in the following Figures.

Figure 5.3: Bending Moment Diagram of Columns and Beams on 2-2Grid (kip-ft)

Figure 5.4: Bending Moment Diagram of Columns and Beams on 3-3Grid (kip-ft)

Figure 5.5: Bending Moment Diagram of Columns and Beams on D-D Grid (kip-ft)

Figure 5.6: Axial Force Diagram of columns on 1-1 Grid (kips)

Figure 5.7: Axial Force Diagram of columns on 2-2 Grid (kips)

Figure 5.8: Axial Force Diagram of columns on C-C Grid (kips)

Figure 5.9: Axial Force Diagram of columns on G-G Grid (kips)

Figure 5.10: Share Force Diagram of beams on 1-1 Grid (kips)

Figure 5.11: Share Force Diagram of beams on 3-3 Grid (kips)

Figure 5.12: Share Force Diagram of beams on B-B Grid (kips)

Chapter 6 Design of Slab

6.1 Introduction

The whole design is carried out based on few considerations and specifications which are given below:

- Design Method : Ultimate Strength Design (*USD*)
- Design Procedure : Equivalent Frame Method
- Design Code : BNBC 1993 and ACI 2008
- Types of structures : Edge Supported floor system
- Building System : Frame Structure High rise Building (10 storied)
- Material properties
 - : 60 Grade reinforcing bars having $f_y = 60,000$ psi
 - : Concrete compressive strength, $f'_c = 4,000$ psi
 - : Normal density concrete having $w_c = 150$ pcf
 - : Unit weight of brick, $w_b = 120$ pcf
 - : Steel ratio for column, $\rho_g = 2$ to 6%
 - : Ratio of the ingredients = 1.0:1.5:3.0
 - : FM of normal sand = 2.5
- Loadings
 - : Floor Finishing = 25 psf
 - : Partition wall load = 70 psf
 - : Live load = 40 psf
 - : Wind and Earthquake load are consider
- Slab Section properties
 - : Slab type = Two-way
 - : Beam type = Singly rectangular
 - : Column type = Tied
 - : Grade beam position = 10 ft. from footing base level
 - : Thickness of all walls = 5 in

Figure 6.1: Panel layout plan

6.2 Design of slab (panel S-1)

6.2.1 Design data

Material Properties: $f'_c = 4000$ psi

$$f_y = 60000 \text{ psi}$$

Beam width = 12 in

Design the panel S-1 as two-way slab with beam by Equivalent Frame Method.

Figure 6.2: Color contour plot of moment distribution in panel S7 (kip-ft)

Figure 6.3: Color contour plot of moment M22 distribution in panel S7(kip-ft)

Figure 6.4: Moment distribution shown from ETABS result file for panel S-1

6.2.2 Check of effective depth of the slab

Maximum moment $M_{max} = 6.22$ kip-ft

Assume panel thickness, $h = 5$ in

Effective depth of the slab, $d = 5 - 1 = 4$ in

$$d_{req} = \sqrt{\frac{M_{max}}{\phi \times \rho_{max} \times b \times f_y \times (1 - 0.59 \times \rho \times \frac{f_y}{f_c})}}$$

$$d_{req} = \sqrt{\frac{6.22 \times 12}{0.90 \times 0.0214 \times 12 \times 60 \times (1 - 0.59 \times 0.0214 \times \frac{60}{4})}}$$

$$d_{req} = 2.58" < d_{prov} = 5" \quad (\text{ok})$$

6.2.3 Calculation of reinforcement

Minimum reinforcement calculation:

$$A_s min = 0.0018bh = 0.0018 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$$

$$S = 0.11 \times 12 / 0.108 = 12.2 \text{ in}$$

$$S_{max} = 2h = 2 \times 5 = 10 \text{ in}$$

$$S_{max} = 18 \text{ in}$$

So, provide #3 bars with $S = 10$ in c/c as temperature and shrinkage reinforcement.

Short direction at mid span (positive steel):

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 3.95 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0048$$

Now, $A_{st} = \rho b h = 0.0048 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.288 \text{ in}^2 > A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$

(ok)

$$\text{Spacing } S = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.288} = 4.58 \text{ in} = 4.5 \text{ in c/c in}$$

Provide #3 @4.5 in c/c in short direction at positive reinforcement.

Short direction at exterior support (negative steel):

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 1.36 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0016$$

Now, $A_{st} = \rho b h = 0.0016 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.096 \text{ in}^2 < A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$

(ok)

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.108} = 12 \text{ in} > 2h = 2 \times 5 = 10''$$

Provide #3 @10 in c/c in short direction

Short direction at interior support (negative steel):

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 1.26 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0015$$

Now, $A_{st} = \rho b h = 0.0015 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.09 \text{ in}^2 < A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$

(ok)

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.108} = 12 \text{ in} > 2h = 2 \times 5 = 10''$$

Provide #3@10 in c/c in short direction

Long direction at mid span (positive steel)

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$
$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 4.65 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0057$$

$$A_{st} = \rho b h = 0.0057 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.342 \text{ in}^2 > A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.342} = 3.85 \text{ in} = 3.5 \text{ inc/c}$$

Provide #3@4.5 in c/c in long direction.

Long direction at interior support (negative steel)

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$
$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 3.15 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0038$$

$$\text{Now, } A_{st} = \rho b h = 0.0038 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.228 \text{ in}^2 > A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2 \quad (\text{ok})$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.228} = 5.75 \text{ in} = 5.5 \text{ inc/c}$$

Provide #3 @5.5 in c/c in long direction.

Long direction at exterior support (negative steel):

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 3.24 \times 12 \times 1000}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right] = 0.0039$$

Now, $A_{st} = \rho bh = 0.0039 \times 12 \times 5 = 0.234 \text{ in}^2 > A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.108 \text{ in}^2$

(ok)

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.234} = 5.6 \text{ in} = 5.5 \text{ in c/c} \quad \text{in} > 2h = 2 \times 5 = 10''$$

Provide #3 @5.5in c/c in short direction

Corner Reinforcement:

Use #3 @10" c/c as temperature and shrinkage reinforcement from the corner of the corner panel of range $l_{max}/5 = (22.92 \times 12) / 5 = 4.5 \text{ ft}$ (1/5 of longer span) for both directions.

6.5. Typical corner reinforcement arrangement for proposed building slab

Chapter 7 Design of RCC Floor Beams

7.1 Introduction

Detail floor beam design calculation considering lateral loadings as per ACI code is discussed in this chapter. There are several beams in the fifteen storied residential building. The building frame model including all beams is analyzed using ETABS. Beams are identified as FB1 which is shown in Figure 7.1. For space limitation, detail design calculation of beam FB2 is provided in this thesis, whereas calculation for other beams is shown in tabulated format.

Figure 7.1: Beam layout plan

7.2 Design of Exterior Beam FB -1

7.2.1 Design data

$$f_y = 60 \text{ ksi}$$

$$f'_c = 4 \text{ ksi}$$

Clear span of the beam = 21.92'

Assume, beam section width, $b = 12''$ and beam section depth, $h = 18''$

Column size, C1= 36" × 15" and C2=40" × 20"

The following bending moments of beam FB-1 are collected from ETABS analysis results file.

+ve Moment at Mid Span = - 138.45k-ft

-ve Moment at exterior support = 81.23 k-ft

-ve Moment at interior support = -155.35 k-ft

7.2.2 Maximum Steel Ratio:

$$\rho_b = 0.85 \times \beta_1 \times \frac{f'_c}{f_y} \times \frac{87}{87 + f_y} = 0.85 \times 0.85 \times \frac{4}{60} \times \frac{87}{87 + 60} = 0.0285$$

$$\rho_{\max} = 0.75 \times \rho_b = 0.75 \times 0.0285 = 0.0214$$

$$d = h - \text{clear cover} = 18 - 2.5 = 15.5 \text{ in}$$

$$d_{req} = \sqrt{\frac{M_{\max}}{\phi \times \rho_{\max} \times b \times f_y \times (1 - 0.59 \times \rho \times \frac{f_y}{f'_c})}}$$

$$d_{req} = \sqrt{\frac{155.35 \times 12}{0.90 \times 0.0214 \times 12 \times 60 \times (1 - 0.59 \times 0.0214 \times \frac{60}{4})}}$$

$$d_{req} = 12.88'' < d_{prov} = 15.5'' \quad (\text{ok})$$

7.2.3 Reinforcement Calculation

Mid Span:

$$M_u = 81.23 \text{ kip - ft}$$

$$h = 18 \text{ ''}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f_c'}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f_c' b d^2}} \right]$$
$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4}{60} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 81.23 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4 \times 12 \times 15.5^2}} \right] = 0.0067$$

$$\text{Now, } A_{st} = \rho b d = 0.0067 \times 12 \times 15.5 = 1.24 \text{ in}^2$$

#The minimum amount of steel for flexural is

$$A_s = \frac{200bd}{f_y} = \frac{200 \times 12 \times 15.5}{60000} = 0.62 \text{ in}^2$$

$$A_s = 1.24 \text{ in}^2 \text{ [selected]}$$

Steel for Int. support:

$$M_u = 155.35 \text{ kip - ft}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f_c'}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f_c' b d^2}} \right]$$
$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4}{60} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 155.35 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4 \times 12 \times 15.5^2}} \right] = 0.014$$

$$\text{Now, } A_{st} = \rho b d = 0.014 \times 12 \times 15.5 = 2.53 \text{ in}^2$$

The minimum amount of steel for flexural is

$$A_s = \frac{200bd}{f_y} = \frac{200 \times 12 \times 15.5}{60000} = 0.62 \text{ in}^2$$

$$A_s = 2.53 \text{ in}^2 \text{ [selected]}$$

Steel for Int. Support:

$$M_u = 138.45 \text{ kip - ft}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85f_c'}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85\phi f_c' b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4}{60} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 138.45 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4 \times 12 \times 15.5^2}} \right] = 0.012$$

Now, $A_{st} = \rho b d = 0.012 \times 12 \times 15.5 = 2.22 \text{ in}^2$

#The minimum amount of steel for flexural is

$$A_s = \frac{200bd}{f_y} = \frac{200 \times 12 \times 15.5}{60000} = 0.62 \text{ in}^2$$

$A_s = 2.22 \text{ in}^2$ [selected]

7.2.4 Stirrup design:

$V_u = 32.80$

Shear Strength of Concrete

$$\phi V_c = 2\phi \sqrt{f_c'} b d = 2 \times 0.75 \times \sqrt{4000} \times 12 \times 15.5 = 17645.51 \text{ lb} = 17.64 \text{ k}$$

Since, $V_u > \phi V_c$, so stirrups will be required.

Excess shear resisted by stirrups,

$$\phi V_s = V_u - \phi V_c = 32.8 - 17.64 = 15.15 \text{ k}$$

Maximum shear strength of concrete,

$$= 4\phi \sqrt{f_c'} b d = 4 \times 0.75 \times \sqrt{4000} \times 12 \times 15.5 = 35.29 \text{ k} > \phi V_s = 15.15 \text{ k}$$

Considering $\phi 10 \text{ mm}$ U-leg closed stirrups, spacing at critical section

$$S = \frac{\phi A_v f_y d}{\phi V_s} = \frac{0.75 \times (2 \times 0.11) \times 60 \times 15.5}{15.15} = 10.13 \text{ c/c} > S_{max} = 6"$$

But, $S_{max} = \frac{d}{2} = \frac{15.5}{2} = 7.75" = 7.5"$ (govern)

And $S_{max} = 24"$

Figure 7.2: Details Reinforcement of Floor Beam FB-1

Chapter 8 Design of Column

8.1 Introduction

The aim is to design the longitudinal and transverse reinforcement for the interior tied column from basement floor to 9th floor. The column dimension has been established as 18 in × 18 in on the basis of the different combinations of axial load and bending moment. Using concrete material of ultimate strength $f_c' = 4,000$ psi and reinforcement bars for both longitudinal reinforcement and ties of strength $f_y = 60,000$ psi. Column layout plan is shown in Figure 8.1.

Figure 8.1: Column layout plan

8.2 Design of column C-2

Reinforcement calculation

Axial force and bending moment diagram taken from ETABS analysis result file are shown in Figures 8.2 and 8.3.

Figure 8.2: Axial force

diagrams of grid F-F

Figure 8.3: Bending moment diagrams of grid F-F

For column bending on y-axis

Maximum axial force on column C_3 , $P_u = 864.59$ kip

Total moment on column C_3 at joint M_u ,

column moment + lower column moment

= Upper

= (53.33) +

$$(133.33) = 186.59 \text{ k-ft}$$

$$= 2239.08 \text{ kip-in}$$

$$\gamma_h = 18 - 2 \times 1.5 - 2 \times 0.38 - 8/8 = 12.49$$

$$\gamma = 12.49/h = 31.24/18 = 0.69$$

Figure 8.4: Sectional diagram of column

$$P_u = \phi 0.8 A_g [0.85 \times f'_c (1 - \rho_g) + \rho_g f_y]$$

$$\text{or, } 864.59 = 0.75 \times 0.80 \times A_g \times [0.85 \times 4(1 - 0.035) + 0.035 \times 60]$$

$$A_g = 267.79 \text{ in}^2 < 324 \text{ in}^2$$

(ok)

$$K_n = \frac{P_u}{\phi \times f'_c \times A_g} = \frac{864.59}{0.65 \times 4 \times 36 \times 15} = 0.89$$

$$R_n = \frac{M_u}{\phi \times f'_c \times A_g \times h} = \frac{864.59}{0.65 \times 4 \times 18 \times 18 \times 18} = 0.057$$

From the strength interaction diagram $\rho_g = 0.035 > 0.01$

The selected column size was 18 in \times 18 in

$$\text{So, } A_{st} = \rho_g \times A_g = 0.035 \times 18 \times 18 = 11.34 \text{ in}^2$$

Use 16 bars of #8.

8.2.1 Design of Tie Bar of Column for a Special Moment Resisting

Frame

Seismic tie design: Column height = 10 ft.

Spacing

$$S_{cr} = \frac{\text{Least dimension of column}}{4} = \frac{18}{4} = 4.5''$$

$$S_{cr} = 6 \times d_{b \text{ long}} = 6 \times 1.128 = 6.768 = 6.75 \text{ in}$$

$$S_o = 4 + \frac{6 - h_x}{3} = 4 + \frac{6 - 0}{3} = 6 \text{ in} > 4 \text{ in}; \text{ So, } S_{cr} = 4 \text{ in}$$

Consecutive cross-ties engaging the same longitudinal bars have their 90 deg hooks on opposite sides of columns

Figure 8.5: Distribution of seismic ties in column

Length over seismic ties are required:

$$l_o = \text{Depth of Column} = 18''$$

$$l_o = \frac{\text{Clear span of column}}{6} = \frac{10}{6} \times 12 = 20''$$

$$l_o = 18''$$

Provide $l_o = 18$ in.

Use #4 seismic ties @4 in c/c up to length 3ft from both beam faces.

Define S_{max} :

$$S_{max} = 4 \text{ in}$$

$$S_{max} = 6d_b = 6 \times 1.27 = 7.62 \text{ in}$$

Use $S_{max} = 4$ in

Lapping tie design:

Spacing:

$$S_s = d/4 = (18-3)/4 = 3.5 \text{ in}$$

$$S_s = 4 \text{ in}$$

Length:

If required, splicing should be given near the mid column length.

Now, Splice length = $1.3 \times l_d$

For #9 main bars, development length, l_d

$$l_d = 0.04 \times A_b \times \frac{f_y}{\sqrt{f'_c}} = 0.04 \times 1 \times \frac{60000}{\sqrt{4000}} = 37.94'' = 38''$$

$$l_d = 0.0004 \times d_b \times f_y = 0.0004 \times 1.128 \times 60000 = 27''$$

$$l_d = \text{minimum } 12''$$

Maximum length should be selected. So, $l_d = 18''$

\therefore Lapping length = $1.30 \times 18'' = 23.4''$

Use #4 lapping tie @4 in c/c up to 4' -2'' length.

Spacing of the bars:

$$S_1 = \frac{18 - 2(1.5 + 0.375) - 9 * 1.128}{8} = 2.76'' c/c < 6''$$

$$S_2 = \frac{18 - 2(1.5 + 0.375) - 3 * 1.128}{2} = 5.43'' c/c < 6''$$

Therefore, no additional ties are required.

Figure 8.6: Cross-section of column C2

(Ground level~ Top floor)

Chapter 9 Design of Stair Case

9.1 Introduction

Depending on the type of the floors there are different types of stairs. The stair is designed for main exit from the basement floor to the rooftop. Here the stair case is designed for flights of a single story only.

Figure 9.1: Measurements of Stair case

9.2 Design of Stairs

Design data

Story height = 10'

Height of the flight = $10/2 = 5'$

Effective span length, $l_e = 12.5'$

Trade	= 10"
Rise	= 6"
f_y	= 60,000 psi
f_c'	= 4,000 psi
Floor finish	= 25 psf
Live load	= 40 psf (3 kN/m ²)
Thickness of waist, t	= 5"
Effective depth, d	= 5" - 1" = 4"

Load & Moment calculation

Load calculation

$$\text{Self weight of waist slab and step} = 0.42 \times \frac{\sqrt{0.5^2 + 0.83^2}}{0.83} \times 150 + \frac{0.5}{2} \times 150 = 111 \text{ psf}$$

$$\text{Total Dead load} = 111 + 25 = 136 \text{ psf}$$

$$\text{(Assume), Live load in stair} = 40 \text{ psf}$$

$$\text{Factor load, } W = 1.2 \text{ DL} + 1.6 \text{ LL}$$

$$= 1.2 \times 136 + 1.6 \times 40$$

$$= 0.2272 \text{ ksf}$$

Moment calculation

$$+V_e \text{ or } -V_e \text{ Moment, } M_u = \frac{WL^2}{9}$$

$$= \frac{0.2272 \times 12.5^2}{9}$$

$$= 3.94 \text{ K-ft}$$

Effective depth check

$$\rho_b = 0.85 \beta_1 \times \frac{f_c'}{f_y} \times \frac{87000}{87000 + f_y} = 0.85 \times 0.85 \times \frac{4000}{60000} \times \frac{87000}{87000 + 60000} = 0.0285$$

$$\rho_{max} = 0.75 \rho_b = 0.75 \times 0.0285 = 0.0214$$

$$M_u = \Phi \rho b d^2 f_y (1 - 0.59 \rho) \frac{f_y}{f'_c}$$

$$\text{or, } 3.94 \times 12 = 0.9 \times 12 \times d^2 \times 60 \left(1 - 0.59 \times 0.0214 \times \frac{60}{4}\right)$$

or, $d = 2.05$ in, which is less than d provided.

(OK)

Reinforcement calculation

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 f'_c}{f_y} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.85 f'_c b d^2}} \right]$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4}{60} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 3.94 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.9 \times 4 \times 12 \times 4^2}} \right]$$

$$= 0.0047$$

$$A_{st} = \rho b d = 0.0047 \times 12 \times 4 = 0.23 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Use \#3 bar, Spacing, } S = \frac{A_b \times 12}{A_{st}} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.23} = 5.77 \text{ in} \approx 5.5 \text{ in}$$

Use #3 bar @ 5.5 in c/c at mid span and will be continued up to both support.

Temperature & Shrinkage bar

$$A_{st} = 0.0018 b \times h$$

$$= 0.0018 \times 12 \times 5$$

$$= 0.108 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

Let use #3 bar as temp. and shrinkage bar.

$$\text{So spacing, } S = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.108} = 12.22 \text{ " } \approx 12 \text{ " c/c.}$$

Use #3 @ 12" c/c as temp. & shrinkage bar above the main bars

Figure9.2. Plan view of stair

Figure9.3. Reinforcement details of stair

Chapter 10 Design of Share Wall

10.1 Introduction

The shear wall surrounding the lift core is 10 in thick concrete wall, and computer analysis is done by the software ETABS as per ACI code.

10.2 Design of shear wall

Design data

$$f_y = 60000 \text{ psi}$$

$$f_c' = 4000 \text{ psi}$$

$$W_c = 150 \text{ pcf}$$

Design data from ETABS Analysis

$$\text{Moment } (M_u) = 3270.93 \text{ k-ft}$$

$$\text{Shear force } (V_u) = 129.93 \text{ kip}$$

$$\text{Axial force } (P_u) = 1730 \text{ kip}$$

Design Dimension:

$$\text{Length of shear wall, } L_w = 13.83 \text{ ft}$$

$$\text{Width of shear wall, } b_w = 10 \text{ in}$$

$$\text{Height of shear wall, } h_w = 118 \text{ ft}$$

Checking requirement of the boundary element:

$$\text{Moment of inertia } I_g = \frac{b_w \times l_w^3}{12} = \frac{10 \times (12.83 \times 12)^3}{12} = 3809158.39 \text{ in}^4$$

$$\text{Stress } f_c = \frac{P_u}{A} \pm \frac{Mc}{I_g} = \frac{1730 \times 1000}{12 \times 13.83 \times 12} + \frac{3270 \times 12 \times 1000 \times \frac{13.83 \times 12}{2}}{380915839}$$

$$= 1723.53 \text{ psi}$$

Permissible stress $0.20 \times f'_c = 0.20 \times 4000 = 800 \text{ psi}$

According to the ACI code, since $f_c > (0.20 \times f'_c)$, so the boundary elements are required.

Dimension of the boundary element:

Thickness of the boundary element, $b_b = 10"$

Length of the boundary element, $l_b = 0.25l_w = 0.25 \times 13.83 = 3.46' = 41.5"$

Minimum b_b or l_b will be equal or larger of the followings:

i) $\frac{l_w}{16} = \frac{13.83 \times 12}{16} = 10.37"$

ii) $18"$

So provided dimensions for b_b and l_b are ok.

Requirement of longitudinal & transverse reinforcements:

According to the ACI code,

$$\text{Shear strength of concrete} = \frac{A_{cv} \times \sqrt{f'_c}}{6}$$

$$= \frac{13.83 \times 12 \times 12 \times \sqrt{4000}}{6 \times 1000} =$$

$20.99 \text{ kip} < V_u = 128.16 \text{ kip}$

Also, $b_w = 10" \geq 10"$,

So, two sets of reinforcement curtains will be required.

10.2.2 Calculation of longitudinal & transverse reinforcements:

Longitudinal & transverse reinforcement ratios will be, $\rho_v = 0.0025$ and $\rho_h = 0.0025$.

Total longitudinal reinforcement per feet of wall, $A_{sv} = 0.0025 \times 10 \times 12 = 0.3 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$

Total transverse reinforcement per feet of wall, $A_{sh} = 0.0025 \times 10 \times 12 = 0.3 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$

Use #5 bars and required spacing [in two curtains, $A_v = 2(0.31) = 0.62 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$

$$S = \frac{0.79 \times 12}{0.3} = 31.6" \text{ c/c in both directions.}$$

According to the ACI code, maximum spacing will be smaller of the followings:

$$S_{\max} = 3h = 3 \times 10 = 30" \text{ c/c}$$

$$S_{\max} = \frac{l_w}{5} = \frac{13.83 \times 12}{5} = 23.2" = 33.19" \text{ c/c}$$

$$S_{\max} = 23" \text{ c/c}$$

So, $S_{\max} = 18" \text{ c/c}$ is selected and provide #5 bars @18" in both directions.

Check shear strength of concrete of wall to resist V_u :

$$h_w/l_w = \frac{118}{13.83} = 8.52 > 2.0$$

Shear strength of concrete with two sets of #5 bars will be,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi V_n &= \phi A_{cv} (2\sqrt{f'_c} + \rho_n f_y) \\ &= 0.60 \times (10 \times 13.83 \times 12) \left[2 \times \sqrt{4000} + \frac{6 \times 0.31}{12 \times 12} \times 60000 \right] \times \frac{1}{1000} = 897.67 \text{ kip} > V_u = 624.33 \text{ kip (ok)} \end{aligned}$$

$$A_{s,\text{prov.}} = \frac{0.31 \times 2 \times 12}{0.31 \times 6} = 4" \text{ c/c}$$

Reinforcement for boundary elements:

$$A_g = \{ (10 \times 18) \times 2 + (12 \times 42) \} = 864 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\frac{M_u}{A_g \times l_w} = \frac{3270.18 \times 12}{864 \times 13.83 \times 12} = 0.27 \text{ ksi}$$

$$\frac{P_u}{A_g} = \frac{1730}{864} = 2 \text{ ksi}$$

$$\gamma = \frac{18-2}{18} = 0.90$$

From interaction diagrams, corresponding $\frac{P_u}{A_g}$ and $\frac{M_u}{A_g \times l_w}$ value, reinforcement

ratio $\rho = 0.0200$

Total reinforcement required for the shear wall,

$$A_s = 0.0200 \times 864 = 17.28 \text{ in}^2$$

Therefore reinforcement required for boundary element

= Total steel requirement – vertical reinforcement required for non boundary elements

$$A_{sb} = A_s - A_{sv} = 17.28 - \left(\frac{13.83 - 1.92 - 1.92}{1.50} \times 2 \times 0.79 \right) = 6.75 \text{ in}^2$$

For each boundary element, use = $\frac{11.13}{2} = 3.38 \text{ in}^2$

Use 11#8 bars and provided steel area = 6 in^2 .

Minimum A_v should be larger of the followings:

$$A_v > \begin{cases} 0.005 \times \text{area of the boundary zone} \\ 2 \#5 \text{ bars at each edge of the boundary zone} \end{cases}$$

So minimum $A_v = 0.005 \times (10'' \times 18'') = 0.9 \text{ in}^2 < 10.8 \text{ in}^2$ (ok).

Design of Transverse reinforcement for boundary elements:

Spacing

Transverse reinforcement spacing will be the smaller of the followings:

First condition

$$S_o = \frac{\text{minimum dimension of wall}}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5'' \text{ c / c}$$

Second condition

$$S_o = 6d_b = 6 \times 0.6 = 3.6'' = 3.5'' \text{ c / c}$$

Third condition

$$S_x = \frac{14 - h_x}{3} + 4 = \frac{14 - 5}{3} + 4 = 7" c / c$$

Since $3" \leq S_x \leq 6"$, so $S_x = 6"$

From above condition, the minimum spacing, $S_o = 3.0" c / c$

Total transverse steel areas A_{sh}

Use #4 bars as transverse reinforcement

Short direction

$$h_c = 18" - (1" + 1") \times 2 = 14 \text{ in}$$

Total Transverse reinforcement will be larger of the followings:

$$A_{sh} > 0.09 \times S \times h_c \times \frac{f_c'}{f_{yh}} = 0.09 \times 4 \times 14 \times \frac{4}{60} = 0.336 \text{ in}^2 \text{ ----- (governs)}$$

$$\text{Or } A_{sh} > 0.30 \times S \times h_c \times \left(\frac{A_g}{A_{ch}} - 1 \right) \times \frac{f_c'}{f_{yh}} = 0.30 \times 4 \times 14 \times \left(\frac{18 \times 35}{16 \times 33} - 1 \right) \times \frac{4}{60} = 0.21 \text{ in}^2$$

Use 4#4 [outside closed hoop + 2 cross ties. Total 5 legs]

Provided areas = $4 \times 0.20 = 0.80 \text{ in}^2 > 0.33 \text{ in}^2$.

Long direction

$$h_c = 42" - (1" + 1") \times 2 = 38 \text{ in}$$

$$A_{sh} > 0.09 \times S \times h_c \times \frac{f_c'}{f_{yh}} = 0.09 \times 3 \times 38 \times \frac{4}{60} = 0.68 \text{ in}^2 \text{ ----- (governs)}$$

$$\text{Or } A_{sh} > 0.30 \times S \times h_c \times \left(\frac{A_g}{A_{ch}} - 1 \right) \times \frac{f_c'}{f_{yh}} =$$

$$0.30 \times 3 \times 38 \times \left(\frac{14 \times 31}{12 \times 29} - 1 \right) \times \frac{4}{60} = 0.56 \text{ in}^2$$

Two legs of the outside closed hoop will satisfy this requirement and no cross tie will be required.

Provided areas = $3 \times 0.28 = 0.6 \text{ in}^2 > 0.6 \text{ in}^2$.

The spacing is 3" in both directions.

The details of reinforcement arrangement are shown in

Figure 10.1: Reinforcement and cross-sectional details of shear wall

Chapter 11 Design of Water Reservoir

11.1 Introduction

To fulfill the water demand of the commercial, residential and other purposes, there are two underground water reservoirs with the dimension of 12 ft × 13 ft each.

11.2 Determination of water consumption

Per capacity consumption = 235 lpcd (BNBC)

Assume, 6 people per apartment

Number of apartments = 40

Capacity = $6 \times 40 \times 235 = 56400$ lpcd = $56.4 \text{ m}^3 = 1990.22$ cft

Two reservoirs, each reservoir volume = $\frac{1990.22}{2} = 995.11$ cft

B = 12 ft

L = 13 ft

Hence, $H = \frac{995.11}{12 \times 13} = 6.4$ ft

Free board = 6 in

So, total height = $0.5 + 6.4 = 7$ ft

Use height = 7 ft 3 in

11.2.1 Design of base slab

Under water pressure = $(7 + \frac{10}{12}) \times \gamma_w = 7.83 \times 62.5 = 489.375$ psf

Weight of base slab = $10 \times 12 \times 13 \times \frac{150}{12} = 19500$ lb/ft

Weight of cover slab = $\frac{6}{12} \times 12 \times 13 \times 150 = 11700$ lb/ft

Weight of side wall = $\frac{6}{12} \times 7 \times 150 \times 2(13 + 14) = 28350$ lb/ft

$$\text{Total weight} = 19500 + 11700 + 28350 = 59550 \frac{\text{lb}}{\text{ft}} = \frac{59550}{12 \times 13} = 381.73 \text{ psf}$$

$$\text{psf on slab} = 381.73 + 489.375 = 871.11 \text{ psf}$$

$$\text{Weight upward force on base} = 1.4 \times 489.375 - 1.4 \times 381.73 = 150.71 \text{ psf}$$

$$M_a = 0.095 \times 150.71 \times 12^2 = 2061.62 \text{ lb/ft}$$

$$M_b = 0.095 \times 150.71 \times 13^2 = 2419.65 \text{ lb/ft}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d &= \sqrt{\frac{M_u}{0.9 f_y b \left(1 - 0.59 \frac{\rho f_y}{f'_c}\right)}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{2419.65 \times 12}{0.90 \times 0.0214 \times 60000 \times 12 \left(1 - 0.59 \frac{0.0214 \times 60000}{4000}\right)}} \\ &= 1.61 \approx 4 \text{ in} < 10 \text{ in ok} \end{aligned}$$

Steel Calculation

For M_A

$$\begin{aligned} \rho &= \frac{0.85 \times f'_c}{f_y} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2M_u}{0.90 \times 0.85 f'_c b d^2}}\right) \\ \rho &= \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 2061.62 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.90 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 9^2}}\right) \\ &= 0.00047 \end{aligned}$$

$$\rho_{min} = 0.0018$$

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0018 \times 12 \times 10 = 0.216 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing, Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.216} = 6.11 \text{ in} = 6 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use # 3@ 6 in c/c

For M_B

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 2419.65 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.90 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 9^2}}\right) = 0.00056$$

$$\rho_{min} = 0.0018$$

$$A_{st} = 0.0018 b t = 0.0018 \times 12 \times 10 = 0.216 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.216} = 6.11 \text{ in} \approx 6 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use #3@ 6 in c/c

11.2.2 Design of Cover slab

$$DL = 150 \times \frac{6}{12} = 75 \text{ psf}$$

$$LL = 60 \text{ psf}$$

$$W_u = 186 \text{ psf}$$

$$M_u = \frac{W_u L^2}{8} = \frac{186 \times 12^2}{8} = 3348 \text{ lb-ft}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{3348 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.0214 \times 60 \times 12 \left(1 - 0.59 \frac{0.0214 \times 60000}{4000}\right)}}$$

$$= 1.95 \text{ in, Provided, } d = 5 \text{ in}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 3348 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.90 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 5^2}}\right) = 0.0025$$

$$\rho_{\min} = 0.0018$$

$$A_{st \min} = \rho b t = 0.0018 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.1296 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.1296} = 10.19 \approx 10 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use #3@ 10 in c/c

Long direction steel

$$A_{st \min} = \rho b t = 0.0018 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.129 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.129} = 10.23 \text{ in} \quad 10 \text{ in}$$

Use#3 @ 10 in c/c at long direction

11.2.3 Design of Sidewall

$$\text{Force, } P = \gamma_w h = 62.5 \times 8 = 500 \text{ psf}$$

Sort direction,

$$\text{Moment, } M = \frac{pl^2}{14} = \frac{500 \times 12^2}{14} = 5142.86 \text{ lb-ft}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{5142.86 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.0214 \times 60000 \times 12 \left(1 - 0.59 \frac{0.0214 \times 60000}{4000}\right)}} \\ = 2.41 \text{ in}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 5142.86 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.90 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4.5^2}}\right) = 0.0049$$

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0049 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.3528 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.3528} = 3.7 \text{ in} \approx 3.5 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use#3 @ 3.5 in c/c at short direction

Long direction,

$$\text{Moment, } M = \frac{pl^2}{14} = \frac{500 \times 13^2}{14} = 6035.71 \text{ lb-ft}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{6035.71 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.0214 \times 60 \times 12 \left(1 - 0.59 \frac{0.0214 \times 60000}{4000}\right)}} \\ = 2.61 \text{ in}$$

$$\rho = \frac{0.85 \times 4000}{60000} \times \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2 \times 6035.71 \times 12}{0.85 \times 0.90 \times 4000 \times 12 \times 4.5^2}}\right) = 0.0058$$

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0058 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.4176 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.4136} = 3.16 = 3 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use#3 @ 3 in c/c at long direction

Temperature & Shrinkage steel

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.216} = 6.11 \text{ in} \approx 6.0 \text{ in c/c}$$

Use #3@6 in c/c horizontally both long & short direction.

11.2.4 Reinforcement details of underground water reservoir

Figure 11.1: Reinforcement details of cover slab.

Figure 11.2: Reinforcement details of base slab

Figure 11.3: Reinforcement details of base slab of wall of the water reservoir

Chapter 12 Design of Water Tank

12.1 Introduction

To fulfill the water demand of the commercial, residential and other purposes, there are three water tanks with the dimension of 11.92ft × 7.4 ft each.

12.2 Determination of water consumption

Per capacity consumption: 235 lpcd (BNBC)

Assume, 8 person per apartment

Number of apartment = 4 per story

Total apartment = 10 × 4 = 40

Total population = 40 × 8 = 320

Total consumption per day = 320 × 235 = 75200 lpcd /day
= 75.2 m³/day

2 times per pumping per day = $\frac{75.2}{2} = 37.6 \text{ m}^3$

Number of tank, $3 = \frac{37.6}{2} = 18.8 \text{ m}^3$

Let, tank height = 7 ft = 2.13 m

Free board = 0.5 ft

Total height = 2.13 + 0.16 = 2.30 m

Dimension = $\frac{18.8}{2.3} = 8.17 \text{ m}^2$
= 87.94 ft²

Let, L = 11.92 ft, $B = \frac{90.74}{12.42} = 7.40 \text{ ft}$

12.2.1 Design of long wall (side)

Moment = $\frac{WH^3}{6}$ (H = 2.3

m = 7.5 ft)

$$= \frac{62.5 \times 7.5^3}{6} = 4394.53 \text{ lb-ft}$$

Required, d :

$$M_u = 0.5 f_c k j b d^2$$

$$d^2 = \frac{2 \times M_u}{f_c k j b}$$

$$\text{or, } d = \sqrt{\frac{2M_u}{f_c k j b}} \quad j = 0.89, k = 0.35$$

$$= \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 4394.53 \times 12}{1800 \times 0.35 \times 0.89 \times 12}}$$

$$= 3.96 \text{ in.}$$

$$\text{Overall depth} = 3.96 + 1 + 1 = 5.96 \text{ in} \equiv 6 \text{ in.}$$

Steel calculation:

$$A_s = \frac{M_u}{f_s j d}$$

$$= \frac{4394.53 \times 12}{24000 \times 0.89 \times 5} = 0.49 \text{ in}^2.$$

Use, #4 bar

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.20 \times 12}{0.49} = 4.89 \text{ in. } c/c \approx 4.5 \text{ in. } c/c$$

Temperature steel:

$$\rho = 0.0020$$

$$A_{s \text{ min}} = 0.0020 b t = 0.0020 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.144 \text{ in}^2 / \text{ft}$$

$$\text{Use #4 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.144} = 9.16 \text{ in} = 9 \text{ in. } c/c$$

12.2.2 Design of Short wall

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Force} &= W (H - h) \\ &= 62.5 (7.5 - 3.28) \\ &= 263.75 \text{ lb-ft} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Effective span in horizontal} = 11.92 - 0.5$$

$$= 11.42 \text{ ft}$$

$$\text{Moment} = \frac{PL^2}{12} = \frac{263.75 \times 7.4^2}{12} = 1203.58 \text{ lb-ft}$$

Steel calculation:

$$A_s = \frac{M_u}{f_s j d}$$

$$= \frac{1203.58 \times 12}{24000 \times 0.89 \times 5} = 0.14 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

Use #3bar,

$$\text{Spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.14} = 9.43 \text{ in} = 9 \text{ in } c/c$$

Temperature steel:

$$\rho = 0.0020$$

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0020 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.144 \text{ in}^2$$

$$\text{Use #3 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.144} = 9 \text{ in } c/c$$

12.2.3 Design of Cover slab

$$L = 11.92 \text{ ft} \quad B = 7.40 \text{ ft}, \frac{L}{B} < 2, \text{ so two way slab}$$

$$\text{Thickness, } S = \frac{2(11.92 + 7.40) \times 12}{180} = 2.58 \text{ in} \equiv 3 \text{ in.}$$

So, provided 4 in

$$W_t = \frac{4}{12} \times 150 = 50 \text{ lb}$$

$$\text{Moment} = \frac{WL^2}{8} = \frac{50 \times 7.40^2}{8} = 342.25 \text{ lb-ft}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 342.25 \times 12}{1800 \times 0.89 \times 0.35 \times 12}} = 1.1 \text{ in}$$

$$A_s = \frac{M_u}{f_s j d}$$

$$= \frac{342.25 \times 12}{24000 \times 0.89 \times 3} = 0.064 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

$$A_s = \rho b d = 0.0020 \times 12 \times 4 = 0.096 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

$$\text{Use #3 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.096} = 13 \text{ in. } c/c$$

$$S_{\max} = 1h = 1 \times 4 = 4 \text{ in or, } 26.4 \text{ in.}$$

Provide #3bar @ 4 in c/c

Temperature steel:

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0020 \times 12 \times 4 = 0.096 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

$$\text{Use \#3 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.096} = 13 \text{ in. c/c}$$

$$S_{\max} = 1h = 1 \times 4 = 4 \text{ in or, 18 in.}$$

Use #3bar @ 4 in. c/c

12.2.4 Design of base slab

$$\text{Thickness, } S = \frac{2(11.42 + 7.40) \times 12}{180} = 2.58 \text{ in} \equiv 3 \text{ in}$$

Let, thickness = 6 in.

$$\text{Total weight of base slab} = \frac{6}{12} \times 150 + 62.5 \times 6 = 450 \text{ lb/ft}$$

$$\text{Moment} = \frac{450 \times 11.92^2}{8} = 7992.36 \text{ lb-ft}$$

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{2M_u}{f_s k j b}} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \times 7992.36 \times 12}{24000 \times 0.89 \times 0.35 \times 12}} = 1.46 \text{ in}$$

$$A_s = \frac{M_u}{f_s j d} = \frac{7992.36 \times 12}{24000 \times 0.89 \times 5} = 0.890 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

$$\text{Use, \#4 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.20 \times 12}{0.890} = 2.5 \text{ in c/c}$$

Temperature steel:

$$A_s = \rho b t = 0.0020 \times 12 \times 6 = 0.144 \text{ in}^2/\text{ft}$$

$$\text{Use, \#3 bar, spacing} = \frac{0.11 \times 12}{0.144} = 9 \text{ in. c/c}$$

12.3 Reinforcement Details of Water Tank

Figure 12.1: Reinforcement details of cover slab

Figure 12.2: Reinforcement details of base slab

Figure 12.3: Reinforcement details of base slab of wall of the tank.

Chapter 13 Conclusions & Recommendations

13.1 Conclusions

A Ten-storied residential building was planned and designed as per ACI and BNBC codes and specifications where lateral loads were also considered. The observations of this study are as follows:

1. Selection of loadings, materials & material properties should meet the requirement of building codes.
2. Lateral (earthquake and wind) loads in combination with gravity loads must be considered in the analysis and design of buildings of height more than 72 ft.
3. Design codes and specifications are different for designing beam and column subjected to earthquake load. It requires more detailing works to achieve structural ductility and integrity for connection and overall strength requirement.
4. We considered non linear equivalent static analysis instead of dynamic analysis which may produce little differences in the analysis and design of the proposed building.
5. Seismic design requires more detailing works to achieve structural ductility and required strength for structural members.
6. External shape of the building structure is greatly influenced on the stability of building structure.
7. The thickness of each panel of the floor slab is varied depending on the size of the panel. However, a unique slab thickness is used for all panels to achieve uniformity in thickness which helps easier distribution of floor reinforcement.

13.2 Recommendations for future work

Based on the scopes and limitations of this study, few recommendations which can be studied further are the followings.

- ❖ Foundation design is very important for building structure but it is not cover in the study and recommended for future study.
- ❖ Torsion of the whole building structure due to earthquake excitation should be checked in the seismic resistant design. It was not covered in this study and recommended for future study.
- ❖ Dynamic analysis method can ensure more realistic analysis of building structure. It is recommended for the future study.
- ❖ Beam-column joints which were not considered in designing the building. Its design and detailing are mandatory according to the seismic design code.
- ❖ Cost comparison is an important component for all types of projects. It must be done before finalizing the structural design of a building. It is not considered for the study and recommended for future study.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Areas of groups of standard bars (in²) and SI Conversion factors

Appendix 1 : Minimum Uniformly Distributed and Concentrated Loads

Occupancy or Use	Uniform psf (kN/m ²)	Concentration lb (kN)
Apartments (see residential)		
Access floor systems		
Office use	50 (2.4)	2,000 (8.9)
Computer use	100 (4.79)	2,000 (8.9)
Armories and drill rooms	150 (7.18)	
Assembly areas and theaters		
Fixed seats (fastened to floor)	60 (2.87)	
Lobbies	100 (4.79)	
Movable seats	100 (4.79)	
Platforms (assembly)	100 (4.79)	
Stage floors	150 (7.18)	
Balconies (exterior)	100 (4.79)	
On one- and two-family residences only, and not exceeding 100 ft ² (9.3 m ²)	60 (2.87)	
Bowling alleys, poolrooms and similar recreational areas	75 (3.59)	
Catwalks for maintenance access	40 (1.92)	300 (1.33)
Corridors		
First floor	100 (4.79)	
Other floors, same as occupancy served except as indicated		
Dance halls and ballrooms	100 (4.79)	
Decks (patio and roof)		
Same as area served, or for the type of occupancy accommodated		
Dining rooms and restaurants	100 (4.79)	
Dwellings (see residential)		
Elevator machine room grating [on area of 4 in. ² (2,580 mm ²)]		300 (1.33)
Finish light floor plate construction [on area of 1 in. ² (645 mm ²)]		200 (0.89)
Fire escapes	100 (4.79)	
On single-family dwellings only	40 (1.92)	
Fixed Ladders		
Garages (passenger cars only)	50 (2.40)	
Trucks and buses		
Grandstands (see stadium and arena bleachers)		
Gymnasiums, main floors and balconies	100 (4.79) ⁴	
Handrails, guardrails and grab bars		
Hospitals		
Operating rooms, laboratories	60 (2.87)	1,000 (4.45)
Private rooms	40 (1.92)	1,000 (4.45)
Wards	40 (1.92)	1,000 (4.45)
Corridors above first floor	80 (3.83)	1,000 (4.45)
Hotels (see residential)		
Libraries		
Reading rooms	60 (2.87)	1,000 (4.45)

Appendix 2: Areas of groups of standard bars (in²) and SI Conversion factors

REINFORCING STEEL BARS

ASTM A615/A706 CHART FOR REINFORCING STEEL BARS						
Bar Size Designation Inch-Pound [Soft Metric]	Nominal Weight lb./ft. (kg/m)	Nominal Dimensions				
		Diameter in. (mm)		Cross Sectional Area in ² (mm ²)		
#3	[10]	0.376	(.560)	0.375	(9.5)	0.11 (71)
#4	[13]	0.668	(.994)	0.500	(12.7)	0.20 (129)
#5	[16]	1.043	(1.552)	0.625	(15.9)	0.31 (199)
#6	[19]	1.502	(2.235)	0.750	(19.1)	0.44 (284)
#7	[22]	2.044	(3.042)	0.875	(22.2)	0.60 (387)
#8	[25]	2.670	(3.973)	1.000	(25.4)	0.79 (510)
#9	[29]	3.400	(5.060)	1.128	(28.7)	1.00 (645)
#10	[32]	4.303	(6.404)	1.270	(32.3)	1.27 (819)
#11	[36]	5.313	(7.907)	1.410	(35.8)	1.56 (1006)
#14	[43]	7.65	(11.38)	1.693	(43.0)	2.25 (1452)
#18	[57]	13.60	(20.24)	2.257	(57.3)	4.00 (2581)

CAN/CSA-G30.18-M92 CHART FOR REINFORCING STEEL BARS				
Bar Size Designation Metric	Nominal Mass kg/m	Nominal Dimensions		Comparison To A615
		Diameter mm	Cross Sectional Area mm ²	
10M	0.785	11.3	100	20% < # 4
15M	1.570	16.0	200	SAME AS # 5
20M	2.355	19.5	300	6.8% > # 6
25M	3.925	25.2	500	1.3% < # 8
30M	5.495	29.9	700	9% > # 9
35M	7.850	35.7	1000	0.6% < # 11
45M	11.775	43.7	1500	3.5% > # 14
55M	19.625	56.4	2500	3% < # 18
UNIT CONVERSIONS				
kilogram (kg) = 2.2046 lb. 1 millimeter (mm) = .03937 in. 1 meter (m) = 3.281 ft. 1 square millimeter (mm ²) = .00155 in. ²		1 kilogram/meter (kg/m) = .6719 lb./ft. 1 metric/ton = 1000 kg = 2204.6 lb 1 megapascal (MPa) = 1 Newton/mm ² = 145.03 psi		

Appendix 3: Column strength interaction diagram with $\gamma = 0.90$

Appendix 4: Column strength interaction diagram with $\gamma = 0.80$

Appendix 5: Minimum & Maximum Steel Ratios as per ACI Code

Compressive strength of concrete f'_c psi	Minimum Steel Ratios ρ_{min}	Maximum Steel Ratios ρ_{max}
$f_y = 4000$ psi		
3000	0.0050	0.0278
4000	0.0050	0.0317
5000	0.0053	0.0437
6000	0.0058	0.0491
$f_y = 5000$ psi		
3000	0.0040	0.0206
4000	0.0040	0.0275

5000	0.0042	0.0324
6000	0.0046	0.0364
$f_y = 6000$ psi		
3000	0.0033	0.0160
4000	0.0033	0.0214
5000	0.0035	0.0252
6000	0.0039	0.0283
$f_y = 7500$ psi		
3000	0.0027	0.0116
4000	0.0027	0.0155
5000	0.0028	0.0183
6000	0.0031	0.0205

Appendix 6: Cross-section Area of reinforcement Bars per foot of slab (in^2)

Bar Spacing (in)	Bar number			
	#3	#4	#5	#6
2.0	0.66	1.20	1.86	
2.5	0.53	0.96	1.49	2.11
3.0	0.44	0.80	1.24	1.76
3.5	0.38	0.69	1.06	1.51
4.0	0.33	0.60	0.93	1.32
4.5	0.29	0.53	0.83	1.17
5.0	0.26	0.48	0.74	1.06
5.5	0.24	0.44	0.68	0.96
6.0	0.22	0.40	0.62	0.88
6.5	0.20	0.37	0.57	0.81
7.0	0.19	0.34	0.53	0.75
7.5	0.18	0.32	0.50	0.70
8.0	0.17	0.30	0.47	0.66
8.5	0.16	0.28	0.44	0.62
9.0	0.15	0.27	0.41	0.59
9.5	0.14	0.25	0.39	0.56
10.0	0.13	0.24	0.37	0.53
10.5	0.13	0.23	0.35	0.50

11.0	0.12	0.22	0.34	0.48
11.5	0.11	0.21	0.32	0.46
12.0	0.11	0.20	0.31	0.44
12.5	0.11	0.19	0.30	0.42
13.0	0.10	0.18	0.29	0.41
13.5	0.10	0.18	0.28	0.39
14.0	0.09	0.17	0.27	0.38
14.5	0.09	0.17	0.26	0.36
15.0	0.09	0.16	0.25	0.35
15.5	0.09	0.15	0.24	0.34
16.0	0.08	0.15	0.23	0.33
16.5	0.08	0.15	0.23	0.32
17.0	0.08	0.14	0.22	0.31
17.5	0.08	0.14	0.21	0.30
18.0	0.07	0.13	0.21	0.29

Appendix 7: Combined Height and Exposure Coefficient, C_z

Height above ground level, Z (m)	Coefficient, C_z		
	Exposure (A)	Exposure (B)	Exposure (C)

0 - 4.5	0.368	0.801	1.196
6.0	0.415	0.866	1.263
9.0	0.497	0.972	1.370
12.0	0.565	1.055	1.451
15.0	0.624	1.125	1.517
18.0	0.677	1.185	1.573
21.0	0.725	1.238	1.623
24.0	0.769	1.286	1.667
27.0	0.810	1.330	1.706
30.0	0.849	1.371	1.743
35.0	0.909	1.433	1.797
40.0	0.965	1.488	1.846
45.0	1.017	1.539	1.890
50.0	1.065	1.586	1.930
60.0	1.155	1.671	2.002
70.0	1.237	1.746	2.065
80.0	1.313	1.814	2.120
90.0	1.383	1.876	2.171
100.0	1.450	1.934	2.217
110.0	1.513	1.987	2.260
120.0	1.572	2.037	2.299
130.0	1.629	2.084	2.337
140.0	1.684	2.129	2.371
150.0	1.736	2.171	2.404

160.0	1.787	2.212	2.436
170.0	1.835	2.250	2.465
180.0	1.883	2.287	2.494
190.0	1.928	2.323	2.521
200.0	1.973	2.357	2.547
220.0	2.058	2.422	2.596
240.0	2.139	2.483	2.641
260.0	2.217	2.541	2.684
280.0	2.910	2.595	2.724
300.0	2.362	2.647	2.762

Appendix 8: Basic Wind Speed for Selected Location in Bangladesh

Location	Basic Wind Speed (Km/h)	Location	Basic Wind Speed (Km/h)
Angarpota	150	Lalmonirhat	204
Bagerhat	252	Madaripur	220
Bandarban	200	Magura	208

Barguna	260	Manikganj	185
Barisal	256	Meherpur	185
Bhola	225	Moheshkhali	260
Bogra	198	Moulvibazar	168
Brahmanbaria	180	Munshiganj	184
Chandpur	160	Mymensingh	217
Chapai Nawabganj	130	Naogaon	175
Chittagongi	260	Narail	222
Chuaddanga	198	Narayanganj	195
Comilla	196	Narsinghdi	190
Cox's Bazar	260	Natore	198
Dahagram	150	Netrokona	210
Dhaka	210	Nilphamari	140
Dinajpur	130	Noakhali	184
Faridpur	202	Pabna	202
Feni	205	Panchagarh	130
Gaibandha	210	Patuiakhali	260
Gazipur	215	Pirojpur	260
Gopalganj	242	Rajbauri	188
Habiganj	172	Rajshahi	155
Hatiya	260	Rangamati	180
Ishurdi	225	Rangpur	209
Jpypurhat	180	Satkhira	183
Jamalpur	180	Shariatpur	198

Jessore	205	Sherpur	200
Jhalakati	260	Sirajganj	160
Jhenaidah	208	Srimangal	160
Khagrachhari	180	St.Martin's Island	260
Khulna	238	Sunamganj	195
Kutubdia	260	Sylhet	195
Kishoreganj	207	Sandwip	260
Kurigram	210	Tangail	160
Kushti	215	Teknaf	260
Lakshmipur	162	Thakurgaon	130

Appendix 9: Gust Response Factors, G_h and G_z

Height above ground level, Z (m)	G_h and G_z		
	Exposure (A)	Exposure (B)	Exposure (C)
0-4.5	1.654	1.321	1.154
6.0	1.592	1.294	1.140
9.0	1.511	1.258	1.121
12.0	1.457	1.233	1.107

15.0	1.418	1.215	1.097
18.0	1.388	1.201	1.089
21.0	1.363	1.189	1.082
24.0	1.342	1.178	1.077
27.0	1.324	1.170	1.072
30.0	1.309	1.162	1.067
35.0	1.287	1.151	1.061
40.0	1.268	1.141	1.055
45.0	1.252	1.133	1.051
50.0	1.238	1.126	1.046
60.0	1.215	1.114	1.039
70.0	1.196	1.103	1.033
80.0	1.180	1.095	1.028
90.0	1.166	1.087	1.024
100.0	1.54	1.081	1.020
110.0	1.114	1.075	1.016
120.0	1.134	1.070	1.013
130.0	1.126	1.065	1.010
140.0	1.118	1.061	1.008
150.0	1.111	1.057	1.005
160.0	1.104	1.053	1.003
170.0	1.098	1.049	1.001
180.0	1.092	1.046	1.000
190.0	1.087	1.043	1.000
200.0	1.082	1.040	1.000

220.0	1.073	1.035	1.000
240.0	1.065	1.030	1.000
260.0	1.058	1.026	1.000
280.0	1.051	1.022	1.000
300.0	1.045	1.018	1.000

Note : ➤ For main wind-force resisting systems, use building or structure height h for z .

➤ Linear interpolation is acceptable for intermediate values of z .

Appendix 10: Seismic Zone Coefficient, Z

Seismic Zone	Zone Coefficient
1	0.075
2	0.15
3	0.25

Appendix 11: Structure Importance Coefficients, I , I'

Structure Importance Category (See Appendix-X for Occupancy)	Structure Importance Coefficients	
	I	I'
1. Essential facilities	1.25	1.50
2. Hazardous facilities	1.25	1.50
3. Special occupancy structures	1.00	1.00
4. Standard occupancy structures	1.00	1.00
5. Low risk structures	1.00	1.00

Appendix 12: Overall Pressure Coefficient C_p for rectangular building with flat roofs.

Appendix 13: Site Coefficient, *S* for seismic Lateral Forces

Site soil Characteristics		Coefficient, <i>S</i>
Type	Description	
S₁	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A soil profile with either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ A rock-like material characterized by a shear-wave velocity greater than 762 m/s or by other suitable means of classification, or ❖ Stiff or dense soil condition where the soil depth is less than 61 meters. 	1.0
S₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A soil profile with dense or stiff soil condition, where the soil depth exceeds 61 meters. 	1.2
S₃	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A soil profile 21 meters or more in depth and containing more than 6 meters of soft to medium stiff clay but not more than 12 meters of soft clay. 	1.5
S₄	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ A soil profile containing more than 12 meters of soft clay characterized by a shear wave velocity less than 152 m/s. 	2.0

Appendix 14: Response Modification Coefficient for Structural System, R

Basic Structural System	Description of lateral Force Resisting System	R
Bearing Wall System	➤ Light framed walls with shear panels	8
	❖ Plywood walls for structures,	6
	❖ 3 storey or less	
	❖ All other light framed walls	6
	➤ Shear walls	6
	❖ Concrete	4
	❖ Masonry	
➤ Light steel framed bearing walls with tension only bracing		
➤ Braced frames where bracing carries gravity loads	6	
❖ Steel	4	
❖ Concrete	4	
❖ Heavy timber		
Basic Structural System	Description of lateral Force Resisting System	R
Building Frame System	➤ Steel eccentric braced frame	
	➤ Light framed walls with shear panels	10
	❖ Plywood walls for structures 3- storey's or less	
	❖ All other light framed walls	
➤ Shear walls	9	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Concrete ❖ Masonry ➤ Concentric braced frame <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Steel ❖ Concrete ❖ Heavy timber 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7 8 8 8 8 8
Moment Resisting Frame System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Special moment resisting frame <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Steel ❖ Concrete ➤ Intermediate moment resisting frame concrete Ordinary moment resisting frame <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Steel ❖ Concrete 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 12 8 6 5
Dual System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Shear walls <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Concrete with steel or concrete SMRF ❖ Concrete with steel OMRF ❖ Concrete with concrete IMRF ❖ Masonry with steel or concrete SMRF ❖ Masonry with steel OMRF ❖ Masonry with concrete IMRF ➤ Steel EBF <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ With steel SMRF ❖ With steel OMRF ➤ Concentric braced frame <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Steel with steel SMRF 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12 6 9 8 6 7 12 6 10

Appendix 15: ACI
cutoff points for

	❖ Steel with steel OMRF	6
	❖ Concrete with concrete SMRF	9
	❖ Concrete with concrete IMRF	6

standard bend and
reinforcing bars

a) Bend points with fixed exterior support

b) Bend points with exterior simply

Appendix 16: Dimensions and bend radii of hooked bars for tensile reinforcement

Appendix 17: Dimensions and bend radii of hooked bars for ties/stirrups

